

PAPER IONOPHORESIS OF SOME PURINES AND PYRIMIDINES

BY S. N. MUKHERJEE AND (LATE) A. R. GHOSH

The paper ionophoresis of the common purines and pyrimidines of nucleic acids has been carried out in presence of an acid, an alkali and a phosphate buffer of p_H 2.2, both in the horizontal and vertical set-ups, as proposed by McDonald and Durrum. It has been shown that reproducible results can be obtained if the experiment is carried out under strictly controlled conditions so that there is no evaporation of liquids. Loss of water by evaporation from the surface of the paper brings in complications like endosmosis, chromatographic flow, etc. This evaporation can be stopped by keeping the current small and applying feed to the filter paper at regular intervals.

In a previous communication (Ghosh and Burma, *Science & Culture*, 1953, 19, 103) the ionophoretic behaviour of the major purine and pyrimidine constituents of nucleic acids (viz., adenine, guanine, cytosine, thymine and uracil) in the vertical migration method of Durrum (*J. Colloid Sci.*, 1951, 6, 274) in a phosphate-citric acid buffer of p_H 2.2 and $N/10$ -NaOH solution has been reported, but the results are different in the experiments performed according to the horizontal migration technique of McDonald (*J. Chem. Ed.*, 1952, 29, 428). Such lack of agreement has also been reported by Durrum and McDonald in the vertical and horizontal ionophoresis experiments with amino-acids. Durrum (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 4875) has not been able to achieve linearity of movement of migrants with time, which has been observed by McDonald (*loc. cit.*). Further, Durrum (*Fed. Proc.*, 1950, 9, 166) has observed the phenomenon of "mobility equilibrium" with certain amino-acids, but McDonald has not. In view of these discrepancies, a detailed study of the paper ionophoresis of the above substances in the two migration techniques has been undertaken in solution of ionic strength of the order of 0.1.

EXPERIMENTAL

The horizontal ionophoresis apparatus was assembled according to the directions of McDonald (*loc. cit.*) but with two modifications: (i) the ends of the paper strips were dipped in separate vessels which were connected to the two electrode vessels by agar—KCl bridge, the purpose being to protect the migrants from the unfavourable p_H changes owing to accumulation of the electrode products; (ii) an arrangement for feeding at the apex (28 cm. high in our apparatus) was incorporated with the help of separate paper strips hanging over the glass support and dipping in separate vessels which contained the same electrolyte solution and were connected to the electrode vessels by the salt bridge.

The purine and pyrimidine compounds, of the purest quality available, were freshly dissolved in the same solutions as used in ionophoresis experiments (concentration being about 5 mg./c.c. in all cases). Ionophoresis was normally allowed to continue

for 8 hours at 220 volts at $25^{\circ} \pm 0.5^{\circ}$. For each experiment about 0.02 c.c. of the migrant solution was applied on paper strips (1 cm. in width) which had been previously soaked in the electrolyte solution and kept in position within the apparatus for an hour with the current passing for equilibration. The possibility of movement of liquid due to some irregularity in the experimental arrangements is ruled out by the complete absence of movement of the migrants without current passing. For detection of the purines and pyrimidines on the paper, the well-known fluorescence quenching technique of Holiday and Johnson with the help of the 'chromatolite' lamp was employed.

Three solutions were selected as conducting media: (i) phosphate-citric acid buffer (Mellvaine's buffer) of p_n 2.2 for separation of adenine, guanine and cytosine (cf. Ghosh and Burma, *loc. cit.*); (ii) $N/10$ -NaOH solution for separation of thymine and uracil (*ibid.*); and (iii) $N/10$ - H_2SO_4 solution for purposes of comparison with the alkali solution.

Experiments in Caustic Soda Solution.—In $N/10$ -NaOH solution as the electrolyte, it was found that in the horizontal procedure adenine, guanine, thymine and uracil moved towards the positive electrode from different initial points of application, although the movement was neither linear with time, nor constant along the length of the paper; the approximate distances moved from the centre were: adenine 4.5 cm., guanine 4.5-5.5 cm., thymine 9-10 cm. and uracil 11-12 cm. Cytosine, however, moved towards the centre from the two ends, while from the centre it moved slightly towards the anode; further, the extent of movement was greater as the ends were approached. Current passing per strip was about 1 mA at the start, but increased to about 2 mA at the end of 8 hours. Water was found to collect on the inner walls of the enclosing vessel, evidently as a result of distillation from the solution. In the vertical arrangement, cytosine did not move from the apex while the other bases moved towards the anode from that position; the approximate distances were: adenine 4.5 cm., guanine 6-7 cm., thymine 6-7 cm. and uracil 8-9 cm. From other initial points of application, all the five migrants (cytosine most pronouncedly) moved towards the apex. Current passing was initially almost the same as in the horizontal arrangement, but the final value was slightly greater. The peculiar behaviour of cytosine will be evident from the following data, which are the averages of three well-agreeing experiments.

TABLE I

*Movement of cytosine in N/10-NaOH solution.**

Initial position of the migrant.	Direction and extent of migration.		
	Horizontal.		Vertical.
26 cm. from centre towards (+ve) electrode	8.8 cm. towards -ve elec.		10.1 cm. towards -ve elec.
13 " " " " " "	3.7	... -ve	5.1 " " -ve
At the centre	0.7	... +ve	0.2 " " +ve
13 cm. from centre towards (-ve) electrode	5.3	... +ve	6.0 " " +ve
26 cm. from centre towards (-ve) electrode	10.6	... +ve	11.2 " " +ve

*Potential gradient was 6.1 volt/cm.

*Experiments in Sulphuric Acid Solution.**—The tendency of the spots, applied away from centre, to move towards that region was again evident in experiments with $N/10\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$ solution, more so in the vertical than in the horizontal method; the spots applied at the centre, however, moved towards the cathode. Current passing increased approximately from 0.8 to 1.7 mA per strip during 8 hours and considerable distillation of water was noticed. The observed movements from the centre were approximately (*vertical*): adenine 6.7 cm., guanine 5.6 cm., cytosine 6.7 cm., thymine 6.7 cm., and uracil 5.6 cm.; (*horizontal*): adenine 5.6 cm. guanine 5.6 cm., cytosine 6.7 cm., thymine 4.5 cm., and uracil 4.5 cm.

Experiments in the Buffer Solution.*—In the buffer solution of p_H 2.2, the movement of adenine, guanine and cytosine was towards the cathode, linear with time, constant along the length of the paper and identical both in the horizontal and vertical arrangements; thymine and uracil did not practically show any movement. Current passing per strip was throughout 0.15 mA in both the set-ups. Even when the electrodes were directly dipped into the same vessel as contained the ends of the paper strips, the change in p_H in 8 hours was only 0.01-0.04 units; the distillation of water was not perceptible even when the feeding arrangements were eliminated. Table II records the migration data (the average of three experiments) of the substances in this buffer.

TABLE II

*Movement in buffer solutions of p_H 2.2 in 8 hours' time***

Initial position of the migrant.	Direction and extent of migration to the cathode											
	Horizl.		Vertl.		Horizl.		Vertl.		Horizl.		Vertl.	
	(a) Adenine.		(b) Guanine.		(c) Cytosine.		(d) Thymine.		(e) Uracil.			
20 cm. from centre towards the anode	6.4 cm.	6.4 cm.	6.0 cm.	6.2 cm.	7.0 cm.	6.8 cm.	0.10 cm.	0.08 cm.	0.0 cm.	0.0 cm.		
At the centre	6.5	6.0	6.2	6.0	7.0	7.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0		
20 cm. from centre towards the cathode	6.9	6.1	6.3	6.2	6.9	6.9	0.15	0.0	0.05	0.1		

**Ionic strength = 0.1 and potential gradient = 1.1 volt/cm.

Mobility Experiments.—When ionophoresis was allowed to continue for longer time, mobility equilibrium phenomenon was observed in some cases. In caustic soda solution all the migrants in the vertical, but only cytosine in the horizontal arrangement came to equilibrium from different initial points of application after about 24 hours at positions slightly away from the apex towards the anode. In the sulphuric acid solution the phenomenon was observed with all the migrants in both the techniques, the equilibrium positions being slightly away from the centre but now towards the cathode. It should be pointed out that with these two solutions as media, considerable distillation of water took place during the experiments and simultaneously the current passing increased considerably. In the buffer solution studied, no such equilibrium was noticed.

*Ionic strength = 0.1.

TABLE III

Mean migration in 8 hours' time in a buffer solution of pH 2.2.
Ionic strength of 0.1 and potential gradient = 1.1 volt/cm.

Substances.	Movement towards.	Horizontal.	Vertical.
Adenine	Cathode	6.60 cm.	6.20 cm.
Guanine	"	6.20	6.10
Cytosine	"	6.95	6.90
Thymine	"	0.08	0.06
Uracil	"	0.05	0.03

DISCUSSION

In order to investigate the reasons for the discrepancy in the two sets of results, the interfering effects of adsorption and electro-endosmosis, if any, on the electrophoretic migration may be neglected since they would be the same in both the techniques. It was, however, noticed that due to passage of current (of the order of 1 mA or more per strip) appreciable heat was developed resulting in gross distillation of water from the vessels as well as from surface of the paper; this increased the electrolyte concentration in the experimental solution, affecting thereby its electrical resistance and ionic strength. Further, as a result of heating the portion of the filter paper, away from the supply vessels, became dry, thus causing the capillary forces to continually siphon fresh solution to those regions. Durrum (*loc. cit.*) has pointed out that this phenomenon results in a flow-rate gradient which decreases towards the centre of the paper. He has explained the mobility equilibrium, exhibited by certain ions in the vertical experiments, to be due to the equilibrium between the velocity of true electrophoretic migration and that of the counter-current flow of electrolyte towards the centre of the paper. The latter velocity depends upon the experimental arrangements and is superimposed on the true ionophoretic mobility of the migrants; further, this velocity varies in magnitude and direction along the length of the paper and also changes during the course of the experiments.

In McDonald's procedure, because of the arrangements of elaborate feeding and efficient dissipation of heat, the drying phenomenon is not perceptible; so, the effect of the above-mentioned secondary liquid flow is negligible and the movements are thus normal as exhibited by the linearity with time and the absence of "mobility equilibrium" phenomenon. But in Durrum's (*loc. cit.*) original experiments no such arrangements are made; so the drying of the paper, giving rise to secondary liquid flow, brings about the abnormalities. That the equilibrium positions of Durrum's migrants are not their true characteristics, but are dependent principally upon the experimental arrangements, is shown by the observation of Durrum himself (*loc. cit.*) that the equilibrium positions are shifted as a result of a profound change in electrolyte concentration after very prolonged electrophoresis.

In our experiments with alkali solution, the tendency of the migrants to move in a direction opposite to that expected from electrophoresis is always attended with heat-

ing and appreciable distillation of water, and evidently the result of secondary liquid flow. The greater movement (towards the centre) of substances applied near the cathode than that when applied at corresponding positions near the anode, as experimentally observed, is probably due to the fact that in the former case the velocities augment, while in the latter they oppose each other. Owing to better feeding arrangements the abnormality is much less in the horizontal technique than in the vertical one; this explains the slight movement of cytosine from the centre in the horizontal arrangement compared to almost none from the apex in the vertical; but the slight deviation of the movements from linearity with time and from constancy at different regions of the paper in the horizontal arrangement testifies that the irregularities, though much reduced, still exist. The exceptional behaviour of cytosine in alkali solution in moving towards the centre from both sides, even in the horizontal experiment, is probably due to a very small electrophoretic mobility of this migrant in the medium used. The results in the sulphuric acid solution can be explained in an analogous manner. In the buffer solution, because of the low constant current, the disturbing factors are completely absent, and the movements are perfectly normal and in conformity with theoretical expectations. The phenomenon of mobility equilibrium in our experiments can also be explained in this light. The experimental observation that the two equilibrium positions of a particular migrant in a particular solution in the two techniques do not exactly coincide with each other is theoretically expected because of different values of the secondary liquid flow in the two arrangements.

Further Experiments in support of these views.—The above mentioned irregularities may be expected to be eliminated in the apparatus of Kunkel and Tiselius (*J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1951, 35, 89) with the paper strips enclosed without gap between two glass plates clamped air-tight, thus preventing evaporation of liquid or in that of Markham and Smith (*Nature*, 1951, 168, 406), with the paper strips bent in the form of the letter V and immersed in water-immiscible, non-polar liquid to dissipate the heat generated by electrophoresis. Experiments employing these techniques or a slightly improved one with the paper strips held horizontally within a tube filled with the non-polar liquid, it was found that the migrants even from extreme initial positions never moved in a direction opposite to that expected; the mobility values, however, could not be accurately determined due to the spots being diffuse.

In experiments with quinine as migrant (the movement being detected by its fluorescence under the 'chromatolite' lamp) it was found that in decinormal sulphuric acid solution, it came to equilibrium in the vertical experiments, but in the horizontal arrangement it moved always towards the cathode, though neither linearly with time nor regularly along the length of the paper. In view of the greater irregularity in the vertical arrangement, these observations are easily explainable. With quinine, alkaline media were avoided due to multiplicity of the spots. With buffer solution of pH 2.2, the migrant, as expected, was found to move towards the cathode quite regularly and to the same extent both vertically and horizontally.

Later on, by keeping the current sufficiently low and constant within 0.1 mA per strip with the help of adjustable resistance in the circuit and maintaining a more uni-

form water sheath on the paper, even in the vertical arrangement, by more frequent feeders, distillation of water was found to be much less in 8 hours in both alkaline and acidic media ; the movement of migrants in a direction opposite to that expected from electrophoretic conditions never occurred, thus ruling out the possibility of the phenomenon of mobility equilibrium. The mobility values were also less irregular than the previous ones, though not perfectly normal.

Thus, the controversy between McDonald and Durrum regarding the constancy of mobility with time and the related phenomena in the two techniques of paper ionophoresis studies appears to be principally due to different types of experimental set-ups used by them and consequent differences in the conditions of operation.

PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY LABORATORIES,
JADAVPUR UNIVERSITY,
CALCUTTA-32.

Received March 1, 1956.